

ISic3036

I.Sicily inscription 3036

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014.09.24 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Modione, contrada Vallesecco

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Partanna, Museo della
Preistoria

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332365

1. Λεφκάνα-

2. ζ.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284831

EDCS 64900409

PHI 332365

Bibliography

- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.0875
- undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1993.0714
- Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II.. Geneva. At 20
- Brugnone, A. 1988-1989. Epigrafia greca. *Kokalos*. 34-35: 337-365. At 339-341 ph

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